

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Molybdenum(V) with *N*-Hydroxy-*N*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*N'*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamidine Hydrochloride in Presence of Thiocyanate[†]

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A new spectrophotometric method for the determination of molybdenum(V) at ppm level has been developed. The newly synthesised reagent *N*-hydroxy-*N*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*N'*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamidine hydrochloride has been used as a chelating agent, and ascorbic acid as a reducing agent for reducing Mo^{VI} to Mo^V. Mo^V forms a ternary complex, with the reagent and thiocyanate, extractable into benzene in strongly acidic media (0.75–4 M HCl) at 470 nm. The method is simple, rapid and free from rigid control of experimental variables such as acidity, volume of aqueous phase etc. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are 3 300 dm² mol⁻¹ cm⁻² and 0.029 μg cm⁻² of Mo^V, respectively. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 3–24 ppm Mo^V. The validity of the method has been checked by employing the method to determine Mo in ores and steels.

ATTEMPTS have been made by several workers to determine the microgram amounts of molybdenum using various reagents¹⁻⁹. Among these, thiocyanate-tin^{II} chloride¹ is preferred for the routine work inspite of its some drawbacks, e.g. the nature of the complex varies with respect to the concentration of thiocyanate, stannous chloride, hydrochloric acid and iron. A number of elements such as copper, silver, bismuth, niobium, titanium, chromium interfere the determination.

In this paper, we report a useful method for determination of molybdenum, based on the reduction of Mo^{VI} into Mo^V with ascorbic acid and their reaction with thiocyanate in strong hydrochloric acid media, formation of Mo^V ternary complex with SCN⁻ and the reagent *N*-hydroxy-*N*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*N'*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*o*-chlorobenzamidine hydrochloride (abbreviated HCPCPCBH) and subse-

quent extraction into benzene. The method is free from the most of the limiting factors involved in the

solvent extraction method. It is also free from variation of position of λ_{\max} and absorbance of complex with respect to reagent concentration. Order of addition of reagent is not critical. The complex adheres to Beer's law. Moreover, the absorbance of the reagent at λ_{\max} is negligible.

Experimental

Carl—Zeiss Specord uv-visible spectrophotometer and Carl—Zeiss Jena spectrophotometer (Spekol) with 1 cm silica cells were employed for recording the spectra and measuring the absorbance values, respectively. The pH values were determined using a Systronic 322 pH meter.

All of the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Ammonium molybdate (A.R.) (1.856 g) was dissolved in glass-distilled water (1 dm³) to prepare stock solution of molybdenum. The metal content of the solution was determined gravimetrically by using 8-hydroxyquinoline¹⁰.

Preparation of hydroxyamidine: A solution of *N*-*p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine in absolute ether was taken in a 500 ml conical flask. To it was added in equimolar proportion, an ethereal solution of *N*-*p*-chlorophenyl-*o*-chlorobenzimidoyl chloride in small proportion over a period of 5–10 min with constant stirring. A light brown oil separated at

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the initial stages of the reaction. Shaking and scratching were continued till the oil solidified into white shining crystals. A few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. The crystallisation took ~ 1 h. It was filtered off, washed with absolute ether (3×20 ml) and dried in air (Found : C, 55.60 ; H, 3.40 ; N, 6.89. $C_{10}H_{14}N_2OCl_4$ calcd. for : C, 55.56 ; H, 3.39 ; N, 6.79%). The characteristic ir bands were obtained at the vicinity of 3 030, 2 560, 1 615 and 930 cm^{-1} .

Extraction solution : A 10% (w/v) ascorbic acid solution, 5% (w/v) aqueous potassium thiocyanate solution and 0.003 M HCPCPBH in benzene were used for the extraction purpose. As the solubility of the free base in benzene was higher than that of the corresponding hydrochloride, a few drops of ammonia solution were added to the solution of HCPCPBH, the excess being removed by boiling.

Procedure : An aliquot of the solution (containing 225 μg of Mo^V) was taken along with 5 ml ascorbic acid (a reducing agent) solution (5 ml), potassium thiocyanate solution (5 ml) and required amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid for adjusting the acidity to 3 M in a total 25 ml of the aqueous phase. The metal ion solution was extracted with the reagent solution (25 ml) in benzene. A time of 3 min was sufficient for full colour development. The organic layer was collected over anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g). The absorbance of the orange-red extract was measured at 470 nm (λ_{max}) against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Maximum absorbance was obtained at 470 nm with a molar absorptivity 3 300 $dm^2 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$. The reagent solution in benzene had negligible absorbance at 470 nm. Benzene was found to be the most appropriate due to high extractibility of the complex into it. The optimum acidity range for determination of Mo^V was found to be 0.75–4 M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The experiments were carried out at 3 M hydrochloric acid.

Effect of reagents : At least 15- and 400-fold excess of HCPCPBH and SCN^- , respectively, were required for complete extraction of Mo^V . A 100-fold excess of HCPCPBH and 2000-fold excess of SCN^- had no adverse effect on the absorbance.

Effect of electrolyte, time, temperature, volume ratio and standing time : The colour intensity was unaffected by the addition of electrolytes, such as NaCl, KCl, LiCl, NH_4Cl or $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ upto 2 M. For equilibrium of the colour system 3 min time was sufficient. The variation of temperature (20–40°) and volume of the aqueous phase (15–60 ml) made no difference. The colour was stable for about 40 h.

Beer's law sensitivity and precision of the method : Beer's law was followed in the range 3–24 ppm. Sandell's sensitivity^{1,2} was found to be 0.029 μg

cm^{-2} . The precision of the method was checked by measuring the absorbance values of 10 samples, each containing a final concentration of 9 ppm Mo^V . The mean absorbance was 0.31 with standard deviation ± 0.005 and relative standard deviation $\pm 1.56\%$.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions for the determination of 9 ppm Mo^V was studied in 3 M hydrochloric acid concentration of aqueous phase. Varying amounts of foreign ions were taken and the colour was developed, and the amount of molybdenum was determined by the procedure described. Chlorine, bromine, nitrate, sulphate, urea, triethanolamine, alkali and alkaline earth metal ions did not interfere upto 3 000 ppm. The tolerance limits of other ions (in ppm) are as follows : Fe^{III} , Cd^{II} , and fluoride (1 000) ; Al^{III} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} (2 500), Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} (1 800), Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} (200), Nb^V and Ta^V (150), V^V (50), W^{VI} (20), and Cu^{II} did not interfere upto 3 000 ppm in presence of thiourea.

Nature of complex : The stoichiometry of the metal–reagent–thiocyanate complex was examined by the curve-fitting method^{1,2}. The result indicated the formation of a ternary 1 : 2 : 2 complex.

Application of the method : The applicability of the method was tested by analysing Mo content in minerals and steel samples (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION* OF MOLYBDENUM IN MINERAL AND STEEL

Sample	Mo%		Standard deviation
	Certified	Experimental	
Mineral**†	2.90	2.89	± 0.032 8
BOS 64a	4.11	4.070	± 0.010 0
BSS	0.85	0.845	± 0.008 8

* An average of six determinations. ** Obtained from Indian Bureau of Mines, Nagpur. BOS=British Chemical standard. BSS=Bhilai steel samples.

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